

Optimizing Fenestration Placement for Enhanced Natural Ventilation in Small Bedrooms

Compiled by Sriram

November 02, 2024

Abstract

This study investigates the influence of fenestration positioning on natural ventilation efficiency in small bedrooms, where optimal airflow is essential for enhancing indoor air quality and thermal comfort. In enclosed spaces, airflow induced by ceiling fans tends to form a continuous loop, with significant velocity along wall edges and diminished airflow near the wall centers. This airflow pattern suggests that placing openings such as windows, doors, and transoms at wall centers may be inefficient, as limited air exchange could result in recirculation of stagnant indoor air. Three configurations are proposed to improve air exchange: corner positioning of floor-level openings, corner placement of full-height windows, and the installation of protruding elements aligned with airflow. Each configuration is designed to enhance low-pressure zones and promote efficient ventilation by directing air exchange paths. The findings offer insights into fenestration design to optimize natural ventilation, supporting health-oriented and sustainable architectural practices.

Introduction

In architectural design, the strategic positioning of fenestrations, such as windows and doors, is crucial in enhancing both aesthetic appeal and environmental functionality. For small bedrooms, where space constraints may limit airflow, thoughtful placement of these elements can significantly impact indoor air quality and thermal comfort.

The movement of air in a room can affect the thermal comfort during the ventilation process (Gong et al., 2006). There are two primary factors necessitating a proper exchange of fresh and warm air in small bedrooms. Firstly, indoor air accumulates carbon dioxide due to human activities, which can lead to adverse health effects if air exchange rates are insufficient. Prolonged exposure to elevated levels of carbon dioxide has been linked to increased health risks for occupants over time (Wargocki, 2013). Additionally, higher concentrations of carbon dioxide contribute to increased room temperature, thereby compromising thermal comfort. This determines the need for consistent airflow within indoor spaces (Yogesh Fulpagare and Agrawal, 2013).

Moreover, the presence of microscopic pollutants indoors necessitates frequent ventilation. If not adequately flushed out, these pollutants also pose significant health risks to occupants (Liu et al., 2020). Thus, an efficient exchange of air between interior and exterior spaces is essential to maintaining air quality and reducing pollutant buildup (Chung and Hsu, 2001).

Natural air exchange within a room occurs primarily due to air movement through openings, such as windows and doors (Heiselberg, Svidt, and Nielsen, 2001), as well as the strategic positioning of these openings (Sherzad Hawendi and Gao, 2016).

This study explores how the arrangement of fenestrations within a compact bedroom can optimize natural ventilation, thereby increasing air exchange with the outdoor environment. Such a design approach aims not only to foster a healthier indoor environment but also to reduce dependency on artificial ventilation systems. By focusing on natural airflow, this research seeks to establish guidelines for maximizing ventilation efficiency in small residential spaces, contributing to sustainable and health-conscious architectural practices.

Literature Review

The movement of air in an empty room measuring 3.6 meters in width, 3.6 meters in length, and 3 meters in height was analyzed in an experiment (Jain et al., 2004). In this study, airflow patterns were observed through smoke visualization, allowing for the identification of distinct regions within the room based on air velocity. A cylindrical cone region, with a 10° cone angle aligned with the fan's vertical axis and extending downward below the fan, exhibited the highest air velocities, covering a significant portion of the floor area. Additionally, a thin region adjacent to the walls displayed an upward velocity, while an intermediate region, situated between the high-velocity cone and the wall-adjacent zone, was characterized by low velocities (below 0.1 m/s). Vortices were also observed at the fan blade tips, along with a flow region entering the fan plane from above. This study further provided a quantitative analysis of air velocity variation across two horizontal planes at different heights from the floor.

Figure 1: Sketch of major flow regions in the room, denoted by roman numerals. The fan has 1.4 m sweep in a 3.6 m × 3.6 m × 3.0 m high room. (Jain et al., 2004)

Another study presented both qualitative and quantitative analyses of airflow characteristics induced by a ceiling fan, highlighting distinct flow regions within the space (Bassiouny and Korah, 2011). The findings indicated the presence of a defined downward flow zone, which could be utilized to optimize seating arrangements, particularly in areas lacking natural ventilation. Results also demonstrated that increasing the fan's rotational speed led to a rise in local downward velocity within the space, suggesting that an inappropriate fan speed may cause discomfort for occupants. Furthermore, the study introduced two empirical correlations to predict the induced air velocity distribution from the fan plane downward toward the floor with reasonable accuracy (Bassiouny and Korah, 2011).

Figure 2: A Qualitative depiction of flow pattern induced by the fan at selected planes below the fan-plane.(Bassiouny and Korah, 2011)

Methodology

To study the airflow within a room influenced by a ceiling fan, a three-dimensional model was developed (Figure 3). This model represents a room with equal length, breadth, and height, featuring a centrally positioned ceiling fan. For analysis, specific planes within the model—abcd, efgh, ijkl, and aceg—were selected to examine airflow patterns.

Figure 2: Three dimensional model to study the flow of air inside the room.

Figure 3 : The movement of air forming a loop represented on plane -ijkl

Figure 4 : The movement of air forming a loop represented on plane -acdg

Figure 5 : The movement of air represented on the floor plane -efhg

Airflow within a room can be observed as a loop created by circulating air, where the fan pushes air downward, which then returns upward toward the fan plane. To analyze this air movement precisely, the loop's starting point is identified just below the fan plane. When the fan operates, air at this point is propelled downward toward the floor by the aerodynamically designed fan blades. Upon reaching the floor plane, the air disperses laterally. Due to the fan's central location on the ceiling, the cylindrical cone region, as defined by Jain et al. (2004), opens towards the center of the floor plane. Consequently, air that descends from the ceiling spreads outward until it encounters the walls, which are equidistant from the floor plane center. Meanwhile, as air flows towards the room's corners, it generates a pulling effect on the air adjacent to the walls, effectively drawing air along the floor plane toward the room corners. **Figure 4** plots the movement of air on the floor, which then moves towards the walls and later to the corners of the floor plane.

The airflow speed along the walls is notably reduced (Jain et al., 2004; Bassiouny and Korah, 2011). Thus, air from the floor plane can only ascend via the room's corners. Consequently, airflow from the lateral and central floor directions converges toward the room's corners. This air then travels along the edges of the walls toward the ceiling plane, or the upper region of the fan plane, before being recirculated by the fan, thereby completing the loop.

Analysis

The study's findings indicate that in a closed room, airflow generated by a ceiling fan follows a looping pattern. Air velocity is highest along the room's corner edges, while it diminishes near the central portions of each wall. Similarly, on the ceiling plane above the fan, airflow is more pronounced near the corners, with significantly reduced flow at the center of each side.

This analysis suggests that positioning openings, such as windows and transoms, at the wall center may be less effective, given the lower air velocity in these regions. In such placements, the exchange of indoor and outdoor air may be minimal, resulting in limited ventilation unless driven by strong external winds. Consequently, without this external influence, the same indoor air may continue to recirculate, potentially impacting air quality within the room.

Conclusion

The analysis from this study suggests a more effective positioning strategy for openings in a room, including doors, windows, and transoms. Typically, bedroom doors are positioned at the edge corners, which proves to be advantageous. Air at these corners can exit through the door, creating a low-pressure zone that draws fresh air from outside into the room. Even with a bed centrally positioned under the fan, the airflow follows a predictable path: it first encounters the bed, then moves downward to the floor, subsequently continuing along the outlined circulation pattern.

Likewise, placing a window in the room's corner could contribute to air exchange. While it may not facilitate a highly active exchange, the higher air velocity along the room edges can help draw a moderate amount of fresh air from outside.

Additionally, the study identifies three effective configurations for positioning openings, optimized according to airflow direction. These configurations are designed to maximize air exchange and enhance ventilation efficiency within the room based on observed airflow patterns.

Figure 6 : Illustration of movement of air according to Configuration 1

Configuration 1: An opening is positioned at the room corner along the floor plane. When air reaches the floor and moves toward the corners, this opening allows the air to exit directly, rather than recirculating upwards. This outflow creates a low-pressure zone that draws fresh air in from other openings, such as windows or transoms, effectively removing warm, used air and pollutants.

Figure 7 : Illustration of movement of air according to Configuration 2

Configuration 2: A full-height window is installed, not at the center, but at a corner of the wall. This configuration reduces the need for additional transoms, as the window serves both as an exit for used air and an entry point for fresh air, facilitating a balanced exchange through a single opening.

Figure 8 : Illustration of movement of air according to Configuration 3

Configuration 3: A protruding element with an opening is installed along the wall edge in alignment with the airflow path, positioned parallel to the floor and open to the outside. This component disrupts the circulation pattern similarly to Configuration 1, enabling air to exit through the opening and draw fresh air into the room.

Reference list

Bassiouny, R. and Korah, N.S. (2011). Studying the Features of Air Flow Induced by a Room ceiling-fan. *Energy and Buildings*, 43(8), pp.1913–1918. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2011.03.034>.

Chung, K.-C. and Hsu, S.-P. (2001). Effect of Ventilation Pattern on Room Air and Contaminant Distribution. *Building and Environment*, 36(9), pp.989–998. doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0360-1323\(00\)00051-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0360-1323(00)00051-2).

Gong, N., Tham, K.W., Melikov, A.K., Wyon, D.P., Sekhar, S.C. and Cheong, K.W. (2006). The Acceptable Air Velocity Range for Local Air Movement in the Tropics. *HVAC&R Research*, 12(4), pp.1065–1076. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/10789669.2006.10391451>.

Heiselberg, P., Svdt, K. and Nielsen, P.V. (2001). Characteristics of Airflow from Open Windows. *Building and Environment*, 36(7), pp.859–869. doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0360-1323\(01\)00012-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0360-1323(01)00012-9).

Jain, A., Upadhyay, R.R., Chandra, S., Saini, M. and Kale, S. (2004). Experimental Investigation of the Flow Field of a Ceiling Fan. *The American Society of Mechanical Engineers*. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1115/ht-fed2004-56226>.

Liu, X., Lv, X., Peng, Z. and Shi, C. (2020). Experimental Study of Airflow and Pollutant Dispersion in cross-ventilated multi-room buildings: Effects of Source Location and Ventilation Path. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 52, p.101822. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2019.101822>.

Sherzad Hawendi and Gao, S. (2016). Investigation of Opening Positions on the Natural Ventilation in a Low-Rise Building by CFD Analysis. *Proceedings of the ... International Conference on Fluid Flow, Heat and Mass Transfer*. doi:<https://doi.org/10.11159/ffhmt16.151>.

Wargocki, P. (2013). The Effects of Ventilation in Homes on Health. *International Journal of Ventilation*, 12(2), pp.101–118. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/14733315.2013.11684005>.

Yogesh Fulpagare and Agrawal, N. (2013). EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION ON ROOM AIR FLOW PATTERN & THERMAL COMFORT QUANTIFICATION. *International Journal of Engineering Sciences and Emerging Technologies*, [online] 6(1), pp.120–132. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/255900047_EXPERIMENTAL_INVESTIGATION_ON_ROOM_AIR_FLOW_PATTERN_THERMAL_COMFORT_QUANTIFICATION [Accessed 29 Oct. 2024].